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Glossary

BCT	Blockchain technology
CINEA	European Climate Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency
CTA	Technical Centre for Agricultural and Rural Cooperation
EIP AGRI	The agricultural European Innovation Partnership
EU	European Union
INESC-ID	Instituto de Engenharia de Sistemas e Computadores, Investigação e Desenvolvimento
INOV	Instituto de Engenharia de Sistemas e Computadores Inovação
NSCE	North South Consultants Exchange
WFO	World Farmer Organisation

Executive Summary

(*Describing the general goals and purposes of the database and the report*)

This report is a supporting document for the Database of pilots/use cases mapped and collected until M8 by the TRUSTyFOOD project at national, European and International level. It briefly describes the methodology used to collect and organise the use cases and pilots, the taxonomy used to categorise the use cases and discusses the main limitations and strengths of the conducted study. It also presents a few representative examples of the type of data gathered. An analysis of the current picture and next steps complete the document.

1. Introduction

Blockchain is an emerging technology, which has received much attention in recent years, with also very conflicting opinions. Such uncertainty on one side, the current partial and fragmented picture of Blockchain Technology (BCT) applications in the agri-food domain and its rapid and unpredictable direction makes it particularly hard for government agencies to make strategic decisions on this topic.

TRUSTyFOOD project intends to make clearness and order and provide the right tools to policymakers on one side, and practitioners on the other side, to make informed choices on blockchain application.

In a simplified view, we can affirm that TRUSTyFOOD applies first the following rule: UNDERSTANDING FOR IMPLEMENTING, that is, it will first map and collect the state of the art for clarifying what does it exist, then it will analyse it. Later on, the project will go more in deep involving Stakeholders for covering those insights which the mapping and collection phase was not able to clarify, for arriving – through a long co-creation mechanism – to prepare the future Roadmap to provide support to the Strategic Research Agenda of the future joint research program as well as some White Papers on important issues which need to be faced.

Summarising, the TRUSTyFOOD project will follow a four phases approach (depicted in figure 1):

- Preparation phase, which comprises the study of currently existing blockchain use cases and projects, that will contribute to the definition of the analytical framework;
- Planning phase, which includes the definition of a stakeholder's engagement plan in order to collect as much information as possible to elaborate the analytical framework;
- Implementing phase, where the analytical framework will be developed;
- Dissemination and exploiting phase where the dissemination of our work will be done.

Figure 1 Simplified view of the TRUSTyFOOD project phases.

As said, due to the novelty and elusiveness of the BC technology, there is no ready-to-use analytical framework yet for assessing its applicability. Along the **Preparation phase**, the TRUSTyFOOD project intends to provide an analytical framework as the 'starting point' for understanding and comparing different blockchain applications, collecting information, experiences and best practices also coming from other sectors, which can become effective in the food domain.

The present document is inserted in this phase, as a first fundamental step for the following ones.

2. Accessibility and scope of the document

This document presents **the results achieved so far on the mapping of existing pilots/use cases on blockchain technology's application** in the agri-food sector and related contexts at national, European and International level. Such results are made public and accessible under the form of Excel file (Database) and also as Dashboard platform for a better user experience.

2.1. What is included

Mainly, the Database reports Pilots/use cases. *A use case is a description of the ways in which a user interacts with a system or product (wrike.com).*

On the other hand, there are also available blockchain solutions, not necessarily described on any use case or pilot projects websites or reports that gives us valuable information regarding the innovativeness of blockchain usage, which will surely contribute to the definition of the analytical framework.

According to the previous definitions and observation, the consortium concentrated on mapping and collecting existing blockchain solutions as well as “pilots/use cases” intended as “tentatives done by users (i.e. farmer, food supply chain player) to apply in own facilities and related operation activities the Blockchain technologies”. Such tentative can be done at the level of “funded R&I project” or through self-financing.

3. Timeframe

Since the interest for blockchain innovation is growing exponentially in the last years, the Database data collection will not stop really at this stage (month 8). This month is considered as a ‘check-point’ to allow the following related activities to be activated (i.e. the use case assessment as well as the Stakeholders’ Engagement process) but the mapping and collection of new emerging use cases will go on, at least until month 24 when the drafting of the final project’s outputs will start. This is a commitment of the consortium, for guaranteeing a real inclusive Database, useful to show to the interested Parties how applications are distributed per country.

4. Methodology

This section presents the methodology used to collect and classify the use cases and to compile the Database. Even if minor differentiation are possible at national level, the overall methodology is here summarised.

4.1. Criteria for the search

- The search was focused mostly on agriculture and agri-food projects and use cases that use blockchain technologies, but also on projects/use cases with a foreseen relation or implications with the agri-food sector in areas such as finance, logistics, IoT and others;
- All the collected information was gathered from public sources in a desk research, but in some minor cases some contacts have been taken with Organisations for obtaining support. It is the case of EIP AGRI [1], CINEA [2], Osservatorio Blockchain & Distributed Ledger of Politecnico di Milano [3], EU Blockchain Observatory & Forum [4]. Interviews at “use case level” have not been performed, being scheduled at a later stage of the project.

4.1.1. Information sources

The main types of sources are represented by:

- *Peer-review publications*

To identify potentially relevant publications, the following online bibliographic databases were searched: Scopus and Google Scholar. The Scopus database was used because it contains the most important digital libraries, such as Elsevier, Springer, ACM, and IEEE. It also provides advanced search and is easy to export. The following queries were performed: TITLE-ABS-KEY ((agriculture OR agricultural) AND (blockchain OR “distributed ledger”). Google Scholar was also used, in addition, so that we do not omit significant papers from the blockchain application in agriculture and the following queries were used: allintitle: agriculture blockchain allintitle: agriculture “Distributed Ledger” allintitle: agricultural blockchain allintitle: agricultural “Distributed Ledger”.

- *Existing databases*

Existing databases known in the field which map and collect use cases were consulted, such as:

- EIP AGRI
- CINEA
- EU Blockchain Observatory & Forum
- CTA initiatives on Blockchain [5]

- *Information available on the web*

With all its limitations, the web remains nowadays the main information source for the mapping process. This is because it is the main nowadays marketing and knowledge source for everybody and also because it allows an easy cross-matching of information.

Starting from the browsers, using key-words (such as web3.0, decentralized web, multi-chain projects, blockchain 3.0, distributed ledger technology, smart contract, next web revolution,

foodchain, foodblock, co-innovation, b-code, and pablock), a search related to blockchain's application has been performed by each partner.

First, the main websites about blockchain technology applications in the specific country have been consulted (e.g. blockchain4innovation: agrifood.tech; forbes.it in Italy). Such websites, as “collector of information on the territory”, were able to provide a quite clear picture of the local scenario. At the second depth level, the agri-food companies' official websites were looked at with a focus on the “News” section. Following, national and regional websites and/or e-newspapers for blockchain applications derived from national projects were consulted. Then, the research focused on technology providers' websites (mainly start-ups). Each information has been examined for obtaining new sources/references and try to go in deep on the news itself.

In addition, belongs to this category also the analysis of EU projects. This mapping was done surfing on platforms such as CORDIS [6], BBI-JU, ECSEL JU PRIMA database, INTERREG CENTRAL EUROPE, etc. In this mapping, the priority was on blockchain technology applications in the agri-food field, anyway also projects addressed to other application fields were recorded and listed in the template. Once identified the acronym, the identified projects were investigated mainly based on the information provided on their websites. Since the main goal was to identify the coherence of the project with the blockchain application, the information recorded concerns the main topic of the project and the identification of the coordinator.

- *Other sources*

As mentioned also in paragraph 4.3.1, another important source used has been represented by the awareness and knowledge of project's partners on existing use cases (in particular in terms of applications in the context of funded R&I projects).

Finally, WFO took advantage of own specific members to collect cases.

4.2. Tool for collection

An Excel file was considered useful at the scope (see paragraph 4.3.2 for more details).

4.3. Practical steps

4.3.1. Partner's task assignment

First, we started by leveraging the geographical diversity of the consortium's partners. Each partner was assigned to search for use cases and pilots from their own countries (either local-only initiatives or applicative cases where at least one member is from that country) and also projects that, while not necessarily from that country, use the same language family. For instance, Portuguese partners researched projects and use cases from Portugal and Brazil. The possibility to have access to information in the own native language was considered useful to increase the number of use cases accessible through public channels (e.g. Internet, articles, papers' publications). Despite being very broad, project partners were also in charge for considering some use cases outside Europe in our search as new ways of using blockchain within the agri-food sector could come from countries outside the EU and immediate surroundings.

Besides:

- INESC-ID and INOV have been tasked with searching for projects and use cases in English;
- WFO, organised in six regional constituencies (Europe, Asia, Oceania, Africa, Latin America and North America) was called to search use cases along own affiliated members;
- NSCE was responsible for searching use cases both in Egypt, North Africa and Middle-East.

4.3.2. Definition of a Template for collection

To guide the partner's search for systems, INOV prepared an Excel file and a preliminary **taxonomy**, presented to the project partners during specific meetings carried out on the month of September 2022. Such taxonomy classifies the use cases according to the different axes of interest and it was progressively refined throughout the course of tasks T2.1 and T2.2 meetings (and related experiences in filling it in) to encompass all the use cases considered.

In more detail, the first step to define the columns was a desk research performed by INOV and INESC ID. The first types of documents searched for were documents about blockchain within the agri-food domain, in order to search for pre-existing taxonomies. Among these documents, we highlight the following:

- Brussels Rural Development Briefings, A series of meetings on ACP-EU Policy Development Issues – Opportunities of Blockchain for agriculture;
- The Danish Red Cross, Mercy Corps and Hiveonline, The Next Generation Humanitarian Distributed Platform;
- FAO, Emerging opportunities for the application of blockchain in the agri-food industry.

With the aforementioned documents, INOV and INESC ID were able to start a preliminary search of use cases, further explore them, and identify some characteristics that could be used to classify the use cases. The result was a preliminary set of fields (non-exhaustive):

- Name: the name of the project/initiative/system;
- Description: brief description of the project;

- **Industry/Sector:** the industry of the project (Agri-food / Financial / IoT / Logistics / NGO / Humanitarian Aid / Healthcare / SmartCities / Others);
- **Main goals,** with an initial set of predefined values: Traceability, Efficiency, Safety, Environmental and Societal Concerns, and Other
- **Website:** the use case/solution's website;
- **Permission Model:** Whether the users of the system need to have permissions/be authenticated to perform operations;
- **Cryptocurrency/Tokens:** whether the system supports any form of cryptocurrency or token;
- **Blockchain Technology:** the concrete technology used (e.g. Hyperledger Fabric, R3 Corda, Ethereum, XRP, etc.)
- **Information Source:** where the description and other information were found.

Afterward, as the use cases were found and submitted by all the partners, changes to the preliminary taxonomy were made to include input such as the difficulty/easiness/necessity to find additional information, which lead to a common agreement among all partners in the current taxonomy. At the time of writing this document, the taxonomy is composed by the following fields:

- **Name:** the name of the use case, project, pilot, system or initiative
- **Description:** a textual description of the project found on source documents/websites
- **Short Description:** a brief description of the project
- **Main goals:** the stated main goals/benefits of deploying a blockchain. These are further divided in:
 - **Efficiency:** concerned with increasing the project's efficiency along one or more of the following:
 - **Process efficiency:** contribute to supply chain efficiency by streamlining the process of product confirmation, authorisations for processing products, etc.
 - **Cost reduction:** contribute to decreasing costs of production / money transfers for specific objectives
 - **Fewer intermediaries**
 - **Traceability:** concerned about where the products come from, which can be further subdivided into:
 - **Item traceability:** considers any physical product
 - **Processes:** tracing processes performed in a supply chain (e.g., production process)

- **Digital asset traceability:** tracing digital currencies, NFTs or any other asset in order to know, for example, where it is used/spent
- **Transparency:** concerned about how the products/services were treated, which can be further divided into:
 - **Item transparency:** any physical product proof of origin and authenticity
 - **Processes Transparency:** know what was done during the processes (e.g., production process)
 - **Digital Asset Transparency:** how was the asset used
 - How food was gathered/stored/processed/etc.
- **Env. & Societal Concerns:** concerned with the improvement in tracking societal and environmental issues, fairer income distribution, crisis funding distribution, carbon tracking
- **Safety:** concerned with the safety of the products/processes along the following dimensions:
 - **Item Safety:** physical objects were subject to safety issues (e.g., temperature/humidity constraints, non-contamination, product test results, product recall processes)
 - **Process Safety:** process control enabling safer processes
- **Authenticity of Documents:** which can be split into:
 - Making documents (e.g., certifications, invoices, docking authorisations, product dispatch authorisation, student qualifications, etc) easily authenticated
 - Using NFTs/Cryptocurrencies and authorisation mechanisms as a mechanism to access services
- **Insurance Settlement:** which can be split into:
 - Streamline the insurance claims and confirmation process more effective
 - Make insurance services available to areas where there are no such services
- **General purpose:** which encompasses solutions designed to tackle a multitude of objectives, with no mention of cryptocurrencies/NFTs
- **Money/Cryptocurrency/Asset exchange:** which encompasses solutions to ease the exchange of money/cryptocurrency or any digital asset for general purposes
- **Records management:** which includes solutions designed specifically to tackle records management (e.g., patient's data)
- **Finance:** which considers solutions specifically designed for the financial sector
- **Digital Identity:** includes solutions that employ non-trivial Digital Identity mechanisms (more than simple user name and password), like Self-Sovereign Identity

-
- **Status of the involved parties:** which states whether the parties in the project are public/government agencies, private companies or institutions, NGOs or a mix of them.
 - **Funding:** which indicates the sources of funding for the project, namely public (EU, national), private or hybrid in the case of a mix of funding sources
 - **Permission model:** which specifies the permission model of the underlying technology and can be permissioned, permissionless or hybrid
 - **Cryptocurrency/Tokens:** which indicates whether the solution supports any form of cryptocurrency or token
 - **Countries:** which lists the countries involved in the project
 - **Inside EU:** which indicates whether the project has members inside/outside the EU
 - **Website:** the website of the project
 - **Contacts:** which indicates contacts of key people that can be used to obtain further information about the project
 - **Technology:** which indicates the blockchain technology used (e.g.: Fabric, R3 Corda, Ethereum, etc)
 - **Single/Multi organisation:** which indicates whether the project involves a single or multiple organisations/partners/companies/public entities
 - **Information sources:** which lists the sources used to gather the information (website, technical reports, news articles, etc)
 - **Deployment:** which specifies where the blockchain nodes are deployed and can be one of on-premises, in the cloud or hybrid for mixed deployments
 - **Industry/Sector:** which indicates the industry or sector of the project and can be one of Finance, Healthcare, Agri-food, Humanitarian Aid, Real estate, Insurance, General, Banking, Retail, Post, Logistics, Art, Forestry, Entertainment, Development and Construction, Transportation, Tourism, Public Administration, Artisan, Jewelry, Smart City, Infrastructure, Social Economy, Education.

From the analysis of the use cases description, it was also possible to introduce the following fields into the taxonomy:

- **RFID:** which indicates (with an "x") if the description of the solution has any hints on to the usage of this technology
- **Manual Insertion of data:** indicates (with an "x") if the description of the solution has any hints on to the usage of this technology
- **Paper document:** indicates (with an "x") if the description of the solution has any hints on to the usage of this technology
- **IoT sensors:** which indicate (with an "x") if the description of the solution has any hints on to the usage of this technology

- **QR Code:** indicates (with an "x") if the description of the solution has any hints on to the usage of this technology
- **Barcode:** indicates (with an "x") if the description of the solution has any hints on to the usage of this technology
- **Smartphones:** indicates (with an "x") if the description of the solution has any hints on to the usage of this technology
- **Digital Documents (excel, word, etc...):** indicates (with an "x") if the description of the solution has any hints on to the usage of this technology
- **Electronic Data Interchange (invoices, etc):** indicates (with an "x") if the description of the solution has any hints on to the usage of this technology
- **Official Websites information:** indicates (with an "x") if the description of the solution has any hints on to the usage of this technology
- **APIs:** indicates (with an "x") if the description of the solution has any hints on to the usage of this technology

4.3.3. Desk research, putting middle of December 2022 as deadline for contributions

Following the above-mentioned methodology, in the period September 2022-December 2022, each partner compiled own local contribution to the database; some partners in the same countries organised meetings for aligning the common activities.

4.3.4. Collection of inputs, clean up and merge

All the single contributions were merged and analysed by INESC-ID and INOV in December 2022-January 2023. From a preliminary check, the database required a minimum of revision.

The following criteria were used to clean up and curate data along the Excel file:

- look for projects/use cases repetition;
- look for the descriptions and get more data from solution website and information sources, as needed;
- complete the fields as much as possible with the solutions website and sources of information, where missing;
- remove solutions without websites or any other useful information, not being able to provide a follow-up.

5. Analysis

The assessment of the use cases is in charge of D2.1, expected at month 12 of the project. However, in this section, we provide a preliminary analysis of key aspects of the Database in the state of the things.

Overall, and at the time of this writing, the Database includes more than 304 use cases.

This exercise allowed to cover 24 EU Member States, 7 Associated countries in European area, and to provide a picture of the International situation as well covering Africa (in particular North Africa), Middle East, America, Asia and Oceania.

The Database resulted too much large to be easily consulted, having to move with the cursor to view the various columns. To provide a quick and insightful visualisation of the underlying database, a Dashboard platform known as Tableau Public was deployed for the visualisation. It is uploaded on the TRUSTyFOOD project's website for providing access to the public.

Here it is the link:

https://public.tableau.com/views/BCStudy2/TRUSTyFOODDatabasePreliminaryAnalysis?:language=en-US&:display_count=n&:origin=viz_share_link

Through the mapping process carried out, it emerged that the Blockchain technology application has three main declared purposes for agri-food companies (Figure 2). These purposes, usually overlapped and strictly interlinked to each other, are:

1. Create a greater supply chain traceability

Analysing the current collected use cases, indeed, 91 cases report that they see in BCT the mean to better monitor and control data along the whole value chain. Additionally, some of the use cases declares that they use BCT to trace a specific segment of the product flow (i.e. exports, picking procedures, raw material supply chain in the respective country of origin) or tracking the entire product flow: from the field to the retailers creating a more reliable food system.

2. Guarantee supply chain transparency

40 cases report that they look at BCT as the mean to build a transparency wire along the whole supply chain with the main purpose to consolidate and enhance consumers' trust in product quality, safety, certifications and sustainability. Moreover, some producers and consortia interested in defend the origin of the product, see in the BCT the mean to protect the product from counterfeiting and fraud. Anyway, a lot of use cases declare that transparency is granted to the consumer via traceability.

3. Provide efficiency (16).

Blockchain solutions on world map

Industry/Sector by Goals

Industry/Sector (Tableau Table 2)1	Main Goal (Tableau Table 2)1													
	Null	Authe..	Digita..	Effici..	Env..	Finan..	Gener..	Insur..	Mone..	Other	Recor..	Safet..	Trace..	Trans..
Agriculture					1	1								
Agrifood	1			16	5	3	1		5	4		2	91	40
Agrifood; Tracing													2	
Art		1											1	
Artisan														
Banking		1												
Education		1												
Entertainment									2	1				
Finance		3		4	3	3	2	2	10			1		
Forestry						2								1
General		1	1	6	7	2	4			1	1	1	10	2
Healthcare				4						1	3	1		
Humanitarian aid				2	3									
Infrastructure											1			
Insurance				1										
IoT									2				2	1
Jewelry													1	
Leisure				1										
Logistics		2		4									1	
Post		1												
Property		1												
Public Administration														
Real estate						1			1				1	1
Retail											1			
Social Economy					1									
Software							1							
Supply chain				1										
Sustainable Agriculture														1
Tourism										1				
Transportation				1	2					2				

Figure 2 Tableau public Dashboard with the general view of the use cases per country, industry/sector and main goal.

Within the use cases in the agri-food sector, they are distributed among the following countries:

EU 27: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Spain, Sweden, The Netherlands (+ Switzerland, UK)

Extra-EU countries: Bosnia and Herzegovina, Egypt, Morocco, Norway, Serbia, Tunisia, Ghana, Ethiopia, United Arab Emirates, China, Japan, Taiwan, Indonesia, Malaysia, Vietnam, Thailand, United States, Brazil

The sum of solutions presented in the aforementioned countries gives a total of 147 use cases taking into account that some of the 91 traceability use cases within the agri-food sector are joint projects among more than one country.

Regarding the use of cryptocurrencies/tokens, the agri-food sector and the Finance sector are the ones with the most use cases. Within the agri-food sector, the goals with the most use cases belong to the Money/Cryptocurrency/asset transfer and traceability goals (4 use cases). Within the finance sector, the goal with the most use cases is the Money/Cryptocurrencies/asset transfer goal (Figure 3).

Blockchain solutions on world map

Cryptocurrencies/Tokens

Figure 3 Tableau public Dashboard with the view of the use cases with cryptocurrencies per country, industry/sector and main goal.

Reported cases explicitly not using cryptocurrencies belong to the agri-food sector, with traceability as their main goal (Figure 4).

Blockchain solutions on world map

Cryptocurrencies/Tokens

Figure 4 Tableau public Dashboard with the view of the use cases without cryptocurrencies per country, industry/sector and main goal.

Regarding the organizational structure governing the blockchain use cases, the ones reportedly having a single governing organization amounts to 39 use cases, 10 of them using a permissionless blockchain, 20 using permissioned blockchain and 9 using a combination of permissioned and permissionless blockchains (hybrid). 30 uses cases were identified as having multiple organizations composing the governing structure, 10 of which using permissionless blockchains, 19 using permissioned blockchain and 1 using a hybrid solution.

Blockchain solutions on world map

Permission Model Versus Governance Type

Funding per Main Goals

Figure 5 Tableau Public Dashboard with the view of the use cases permission model, governance type, funding and main goals.

Regarding the Use Cases funding, focusing our attention to the Traceability Use Cases, 37 were EU funded, 2 recurred to other type of public funding (not EU), 8 had national funding (outside EU), 41 was privately funded, and 1 was funded recurring to public and private funds. We can conclude also that single organization with permissioned solutions are the most common for the traceability goal (12 Use Cases), and second comes the permissioned solutions with multiple organizations (9 use cases).

Blockchain solutions on world map

Permission Model Versus Governance Type

Funding per Main Goals

Figure 6 Tableau Public Dashboard with the view of the use cases permission model, governance type, funding and main goals, filtered for the traceability use cases.

Focusing now on the Agri-food industry, we found out that most of the use cases reporting their funding was EU funded (57), 48 were privately funded, and 5 were nationally funded. Most of the solutions were deployed with a permissioned blockchain, 21 in total, 12 being managed by a single organization.

Blockchain solutions on world map

Permission Model Versus Governance Type

Permission model
 Hybrid
 Permissioned
 Permissionless

Funding per Industry/Sector

Figure 7 Tableau Public Dashboard with the view of the use cases permission model, governance type, funding and industry/sector, filtered for the Agri-food sector.

6. Strengths and limitations of the study

We identified the following limitations, which we discuss next:

- Sometimes, information is not updated since some time, meaning that some solutions are no longer available, as well as their websites and contacts;
- It is to be expected that the consortium was able to map and collect some (not all) use cases. This shortcoming will be tried to be overcome through the actions mentioned in the paragraphs 3 and 7.
- Another limitation is related to the geographicity of the partners involved into the search. Since each partner was responsible for collecting data about projects from own country and in the local language, the Database can naturally over-represent use cases coming from the partners' countries of origin. We mitigate this limitation first starting from existing databases (already mentioned along the text), then by having two partners (INESC-ID and INOV) able to perform additional search for projects in English; not at

least, consulting funded R&I projects which usually involve players from different countries.

In addition, our research scope returned heterogeneous data that were not easy to classify for conducting the study. For example, some of these data sources do not make a distinction between use cases/ projects, consulting services, initiatives, blockchain associations, and so on. Furthermore, restricting ourselves to publicly available data, the public information was often inconclusive for defining certain categories of the taxonomy challenging the proper classification of projects concerning these categories. As an example, consulting the agri-food companies' official websites, with a focus on the "News" section, in most cases the communication of blockchain technology applications is explained from a marketing point of view and focuses on the technology's capability to create trust along the food chain and towards the consumers. No technical details about the type of technology adopted, permission model, or deployment are provided. In these cases, this information was left blank. Also considering national and regional websites and/or e-newspapers for blockchain applications derived from national projects, the information provided focuses on the purpose and the efficiency that blockchain technology has while information about the type of technology applied, the model's permission level, and the deployment are not specified. Technology providers' websites provide access to their specific use cases thanks to a dedicated section that highlights their collaboration with food companies, but not enough details are provided to cover our taxonomy.

We intend to mitigate this shortcoming by providing at this stage the data sources we used and, as a next step, entering in contact with most of these such use cases' referents to cover the current gaps.

- Finally, as a limitation, it should be noted that in most of the public available reports and databases agri-food cases resulted very few compared to applications in other sectors. This increased the difficulty in identifying and extrapolating the data of interest in a statistical representative amount.

On the other hand, and to the best of our knowledge, our approach enabled us to:

- extend and organize the existing public sources of information;
- structure the existing information, focussing on the agri-food and other related sectors;
- document solutions that were not present in any other studies regarding blockchain and agri-food.

7. Next steps

As anticipated in paragraph 3, the Database (and the related Dashboard) will be continuously improved (up to M24 of the project).

The strategy planned inside the consortium to facilitate such process is the following:

1. Engaging with new funded projects for mapping and collecting new use cases and related evidences,

2. Asking to the scientific community, through Social Media communication channels and the project's website, to directly contribute. Indeed, a Template for including own use case will be provided soon online. The organisation/user will fill the template in and send back through the automatized system. An internal process of pre-evaluation of data provided is foreseen before its acceptance and integration into the Database and related Dashboard,
3. As we develop our work in the forthcoming tasks and work packages, we will have the opportunity to engage several other entities directly, that could enrich our database with more use cases.

The Database at the time of writing will represent the starting point for assessing the use cases and understand the current landscape related to Blockchain application in Agriculture and food system.

The Database will include also cases related to organic supply chains, as well as new value chains, which start from agriculture for moving towards new fields of the bioeconomy.

8. References

[1] https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/find-connect/projects?search_api_views_fulltext_op=OR&search_api_views_fulltext=&field_core_keywords%5B%5D=3548&field_proj_funding_source_list=All

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[3] <https://www.osservatori.net/it/home>

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